

Face Recognition Technique for Fighting Insurgency in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive study on the application of face recognition techniques in the context of combating insurgency in Nigeria. The growing threat of insurgency has posed significant challenges to national security and necessitated innovative approaches to identify and apprehend perpetrators. Face recognition technology has emerged as a promising tool for enhancing surveillance and intelligence-gathering capabilities in counterinsurgency operations. The research begins by examining the unique characteristics of insurgency in Nigeria and the limitations of traditional identification methods. It then delves into the fundamentals of face recognition, exploring various algorithms and methodologies employed in the field. Additionally, the paper investigates the specific challenges faced in deploying face recognition systems in the Nigerian context, such as diverse ethnicities, environmental conditions, and limited resources. The study presents a detailed analysis of existing face recognition techniques and evaluates their effectiveness in real-world scenarios. It also explores the ethical considerations and privacy concerns associated with deploying such systems. Furthermore, the paper discusses the integration of face recognition technology with other surveillance and intelligence systems to create a comprehensive framework for fighting insurgency. The findings of this research contribute to the development of tailored strategies and solutions for leveraging face recognition in the Nigerian counterinsurgency efforts. The study emphasizes the potential of this technology to enhance situational awareness, expedite suspect identification, and support proactive decision-making. The insights gained from this research can guide policymakers, security agencies, and technology developers in effectively leveraging face recognition for a safer and more secure Nigeria.

Keywords: face recognition, insurgency in Nigeria, counterinsurgency, surveillance, security, facial characteristics,

1. Introduction

The nature of warfare has undergone a significant transformation, compelling our military and government to adapt and effectively combat and triumph in this new landscape. Presently, we find ourselves engaged

in a global counterinsurgency, an unparalleled challenge that demands original strategic thinking and a profound comprehension comparable, perhaps, only to the complexities of the Cold War. Our continuous political-military endeavors to achieve success in Nigeria's Sambisa forest, Maidugiri, Bauchi, and other insurgency-ridden regions are merely subordinate efforts in the broader, intricate global conflict. Our adversaries, represented by Boko Haram, have astutely recognized the strategic advantages of employing asymmetrical approaches to counter the overwhelming conventional might of the United States military. Regrettably, our unmatched conventional capabilities have impeded the Nigerian army's response to the evolving, asymmetrical nature of modern warfare.

The Nigerian military faces the peril of failing to grasp the true essence of the war we are currently waging—an intelligence-intensive conflict shaped by perceptions. Consequently, we must confront this predicament head-on and elevate our thinking to a new strategic plane in this era. This entails comprehending the necessary tools and strategic methodologies required to secure victory in this vastly distinct 21st-century environment.

2. A review of the literatures on face recognition systems

According to John (2017), insurgency can be defined as an organized movement that aims to overthrow a legitimate government through subversion and armed conflict. Insurgency movements typically emerge from a desire for social and/or political change, utilizing guerrilla warfare tactics to achieve their objectives. It is essential to distinguish between insurgencies and insurgency movements, as counterinsurgent operations encompass more than just countering the insurgency's military force, unlike counter-guerrilla operations. In this article, the term "counterinsurgency" refers to comprehensive operations that target the insurgency politically, economically, and militarily, as highlighted by Vimal (2015).

Successful insurgencies rely on certain fundamental prerequisites, as outlined in the Field Manual (FM) on Foreign Internal Defense Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures for Special Forces. These prerequisites include a vulnerable population, strong leadership, and a lack of government control. The primary requirement is the positive support, or at the very least, the compliance of the population. Mao Tse-tung (2015) observed that guerrilla warfare derives its strength and sustenance from the masses, making their

sympathy and cooperation indispensable for its existence and success. Insurgencies capitalize on a vulnerable population, charismatic leaders, and a government's inability to maintain control, enabling them to gain popular support in a more efficient and effective manner.

Insurgencies require ongoing popular support, which should ideally increase as the movement progresses. Initially, support is crucial for the insurgency to transition from an abstract concept to a tangible and active movement. As the government responds and defends its power, the insurgency continues to rely on support. With time, the insurgency may shift from guerrilla tactics to conventional warfare, aiming to dismantle the national power structure and expand its territorial control. During this process, violence escalates, and the insurgency must justify it as necessary for achieving goals that garner public backing, such as improved security and justice. Swati et al. (2013)

Maintaining and growing popular support is achieved through effective communication, both through media channels and by treating civilians respectfully. While the importance of communication remains consistent, globalization has influenced the way insurgencies utilize media for internal and external messaging. Initially, insurgencies rely on secrecy to protect their vulnerable organization, but the need for communication remains high. Fortunately, technological advancements have largely resolved this challenge.

i. The Influence of the Internet on Global Insurgency: Effects on Communication, Organizational Structures, and Propagation

Fortunately for the insurgents, a combination of two groundbreaking technologies, namely the Internet and user-friendly "strong-encryption," has provided them with a solution to their operational security predicament. The Internet, in particular, has profoundly revolutionized insurgent communications, operations, and organizational capabilities.

One of the most notable and significant impacts of the Internet lies in the realm of communication. Insurgents now have a wide range of communication options at their disposal, including e-mail, instant messaging, chat rooms, websites, blogs, Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP), and other related technologies. This diverse array of communication channels presents a challenge for counterinsurgents, who must monitor this expanding cyber-universe while addressing operational security concerns similar to those found in mobile/satellite phone networks (Swati et al., 2013).

Furthermore, the counterinsurgents face an additional hurdle due to the widespread availability of strong-encryption software freely accessible on the Internet. The advent of Pretty Good Privacy (PGP) 1.0 in 1991 revolutionized secure communications by providing average computer users with simplified access to complex encryption algorithms. As a result, electronic communications employing such encryption methods have become incredibly difficult, if not impossible, to decipher. The continuous development of newer software and versions, including numerous iterations of PGP, further strengthens this technology. Currently, efforts are underway to adapt this level of security to voice communications (Vimal, 2015).

Moreover, the Internet enables insurgent groups to reach a broad audience, both within and outside the targeted country. Through the dissemination of information via the Internet, globalization has expanded the insurgency's ability to propagate its message to individuals who previously would not have had access to it. Insurgent and terrorist organizations have swiftly embraced the Internet and mobile phones to spread propaganda, recruit fighters, and seek arms and financial support. Geographical constraints and the need for physical distribution of literature no longer restrict insurgencies. For instance, organizations like Hamas can find a receptive audience in a living room in Middle America as well as in a fundamentalist madrasah in the Middle East.

The impact of the Internet on insurgent operations is significant. It provides insurgents with a distinct operational platform that goes beyond traditional battlefields. Insurgencies have shown adeptness in recognizing and utilizing these new technologies. Hackers affiliated with insurgent movements in various countries have launched attacks on corporate and government websites, defaced them, and created computer viruses to support their cause or spread their political agenda. This phenomenon is observed in Serbia, Indonesia, Mexico, India, Iran, Nigeria, Hungary, England, Bolivia, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Palestine, and the United States.

Insurgencies constantly strive to enhance their operational effectiveness by achieving their goals more efficiently while evading capture, injury, or death. To do so, they actively seek information to learn, adapt, and develop their strategies. The acquisition of information has both temporary and lasting components. The full implications of the Internet's impact on insurgency operations are not fully understood yet, but it is clear that insurgents have embraced and harnessed these new technologies to further their objectives, Swati, P., et al. (2013).

This text highlights the immediate benefits that insurgency gains from incoming information, which is primarily tactical in nature. The Internet serves as a valuable source of such information, with numerous news sites, military-interest sites, and military-related blogs offering a wealth of data. One example is

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Globalsecurity.org, which provides comprehensive information on counterinsurgent forces in Iraq, including descriptions and locations of camps, troop levels, combat operations, and detailed analysis of weapons systems. Notably, it also offers high-resolution satellite imagery of coalition troop positions, including vulnerable sleeping trailers. Google Earth, another source, provides similar information and has faced public protests from countries like India, Thailand, and South Korea due to security concerns.

Additionally, insurgents utilize the internet to access information on the manufacturing of improvised explosive devices (IEDs). While traditional books on this subject can be found on websites like Amazon.com, the proliferation of online resources has made it easier for insurgents to acquire this knowledge (Vimal, 2015).

Overall, the text highlights how insurgents exploit readily available online information to gain tactical advantages and underscores the importance of understanding and addressing these dynamics in counterinsurgency efforts.

The impact of the Internet on insurgency organization and structure is closely connected to, yet distinct from, its influence on communications and operations. The widespread availability of information technologies has brought unexpected advantages to present-day insurgencies. Although it has weakened leaders' control over information, diminishing their authority and power, the overall effect on the insurgency is positive. Instead of having centralized control over information dissemination and retention, insurgent groups have evolved into decentralized entities with minimal hierarchical organization, resulting in reduced vulnerability. Scholars John Arquilla and David Ronfeldt (2017) have coined the term "netwar" to describe this organizational shift, characterized by network-based forms of organization, doctrine, strategy, and communication. The lack of a central focus makes countering such an organization challenging for counterinsurgents.

A 2004 RAND study documented this phenomenon in Iraq, revealing the absence of clear leadership, territorial control ambitions, and a unified ideology among the insurgency. However, the current situation in Iraq presents a somewhat different picture. Certain elements of the insurgency have gained physical control or attempted to control specific areas, such as Najaf, Karbala, Ramadi, Sadr City, and Falluja. Moreover, these disparate elements seem to have embraced a shared purpose, namely creating insecurity in the population to drive out occupying forces. Nevertheless, what remains absent is a unified leadership for the entire insurgency, despite some elements having identifiable leaders and hierarchical structures.

Interpreting these observations, Iraq appears to exhibit a hybrid insurgency, blending elements of traditional insurgency with characteristics associated with netwar. Alternatively, one could argue that the situation in Iraq reflects multiple independent insurgencies, each developing autonomously in the classical sense. The exact categorization of the insurgency is subject to ongoing debate, contingent upon the level of communication and coordination between its diverse elements. Regardless of the interpretation, eliminating one element, including senior leaders, merely gives rise to new micro-insurgencies or knowledgeable insurgents. The insurgency has effectively decentralized its command, control, and intelligence, making it impossible for the counterinsurgent to exclusively target the insurgency through tactical force.

ii. *What makes Face Recognition the preferred choice among various Biometric Methods*

While methods like fingerprints, iris scans, and voice recognition are viable for identification, they may not be the most suitable options in certain scenarios. For instance, when it comes to surveillance and monitoring of public places, these traditional methods can be time-consuming and inefficient, especially when dealing with a large number of people. Additionally, the cost of implementing such systems can be a hindrance, as some components often need to be imported, making the setup expensive.

As a solution, face recognition emerges as a favorable alternative. Takeo Kanade, a renowned Japanese computer scientist specializing in computer vision, developed a program that extracts facial feature points (such as nose, eyes, ears, and mouth) from photographs. These extracted features are then compared to reference data for identification purposes. The use of face recognition offers several advantages in terms of convenience and efficiency. Unlike other biometric methods that require physical contact or specific actions from individuals, face recognition does not necessitate individuals to line up and provide fingerprints or subject themselves to iris scans. This makes face recognition a more practical and user-friendly option for various applications.(Vimal, 2015). The text highlights significant milestones in the development of automated face recognition techniques. In 1987, Sirovich and Kirby introduced the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method, demonstrating that a small number of values could accurately represent a properly aligned and normalized face image.

Turk and Pentland furthered the research by discovering that residual errors from the Eigen faces technique could be used to detect faces in images, enabling real-time automatic face recognition systems. Despite some limitations related to environmental factors, this approach generated significant interest in advancing automated face recognition. The Viola-Jones Adaboost and Haar cascade method revolutionized visual detection by combining new algorithms and insights. It distinguished itself by its ability to rapidly detect faces, achieving 15 frames per second on a 384 x 288 pixel image using a 700MHz Intel Pentium 3 Processor.

The text also outlines the four stages of identification or authentication technologies: capture, extraction, comparison, and match/non-match. These stages involve capturing a sample, extracting unique data to create a template, comparing the template with a new sample, and determining whether the features extracted from the new sample are a match or non-match.

Overall, the milestones mentioned in the text have played a crucial role in advancing the field of automated face recognition, leading to more efficient and reliable systems.

iii. System Design Methodology

The text describes the selection of the iterative waterfall model for the system development life cycle (SDLC). This model follows a series of events starting from requirement definition, system and software design, implementation and unit testing, integration and system testing, and operational maintenance. While primarily utilizing the waterfall model, the development process also incorporates elements from other models, such as prototyping.

Prototyping aided in system definition and analysis, as well as the creation of data flow diagrams. The Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) was employed to illustrate the relationships between entities, while Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) depicted the flow of data within the system.

The choice of the iterative waterfall model was motivated by its division of the SDLC into distinct phases. Each phase involved well-defined activities, such as the analysis stage that focused on structured analysis of requirements, particularly regarding the functionality of data flow at a basic security station (police). The system and structured analysis were then transformed into software design, which included defining software architecture, decomposing the system into modules, representing relationships among the modules, and designing data structures and algorithms for the modules.

Overall, the iterative waterfall model was chosen to guide the system development process, ensuring a structured approach and addressing specific requirements and functionality related to data flow at a security station.

The diagram below is a high level view of the new system with the main components of the system and the services they provide and how they communicate. The system is implemented using a three-tier architecture that comprises of user interface, process management and DBMS as illustrated below.

Figure 1: dataflow diagram

iv. *Design processes and stages*

In this section, the various processes adopted for the development of the proposed system were discussed.

- *Image capture:*

This process involves capturing the facial image using a HD image acquisition device (quality of image is important). It is implemented using the image acquisition tool in matlab.

- *Face detection:*

This employs computer vision tool to detect human face and facial features using the viola and jones algorithm specially developed for face tracking and detection.

- *Image Binarization:*

This process converts the facial image into a bi-level in preparation for preprocessing. Histogram equalization and transformation: this is a preliminary processing techniques employed to enhance the image and eliminate background noise.

- *Edge Detection:*

This method simplifies and minimizes the image data to be processed. “Edge detection begins with the examination of the local discontinuity at each pixel element in an image amplitude, orientation, and location of a particular subarea in the image that is of interest. Also it detects the boundary between two homogeneous regions and finds out the outlines of an image background. “This process of partitioning a digital image into multiple regions or set of pixels is called image segmentation”.

- *Image Normalization:*

Once the face and its features are segmented, the next stage is to normalize these face parts, to enable generation of general facial analysis through feature extraction. The normalization process help achieve constant illumination in the facial image.

- *Bag of Feature extraction :*

This is the final step of the image processing step. This involves a statistical method of dimensionality reduction that represents the discriminative part of the image in a compact feature vector, this is implemented with matlab using the histogram of oriented gradient technique to extract the training and label features. The feature extracted are called bag of statistical features from both the query (y) and training dataset (x).

- *Recognition:*

Based on the feature extraction techniques of statistical method that extracts large amount of statistical values from the face, a machine learning algorithm is required for the classification and training of the extracted features hence a supervised machine is employed under the holistic approach to classify and train the extracted features for recognition.

- *Training and Classification:*

For the training and classification of the statistical extracted features, we employ a supervised machine learning technique called the k-nearest neighbor classifiers. It is a simple algorithm and a non-parametric method that classifies data based on similarity measures such as distance metrics which are defined by the standard Euclidean distance and Euclidean distance. Given an $m1$ -by- n data matrix X , which is treated as $m1$ (1-by- n) row vectors $x_1, x_2, \dots, \dots, x_{m1}$, and $m2$ -by- n data matrix Y , which is treated as $m2$ (1-by- n) row vectors $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{m2}$, the various distances between the vector x_s and y_t are defined as follows :

Euclidean distance: $d_{st}^2 = (x_s - y_t)(x_s - y_t)^T$ - - - (i)

Standardized Euclidean distance:

$d_{st}^2 = (x_s - y_t)V^{-1}(x_s - y_t)^T$ - - - (ii)

Where V is the m -by- n diagonal matrix whose j the diagonal element is $S(j)^2$, where S is the vector containing the inverse weights.

Prediction of Label (Result)

For the prediction of the classified label: the mathematics function below is employed as in [.

$q = \arg \min_{q=1, \dots, k} \sum_{k=1}^k T\left(\frac{k}{x}\right) C\left(\frac{q}{k}\right)$ - - - (iii)

Where: q is the predicted classification.

k is the number of classes.

$T\left(\frac{k}{x}\right)$ is the posterior probability of class k for observation x .

$C\left(\frac{q}{k}\right)$ is the cost of classifying an observation as y when its true class is k

Implementing the function given a set x of n points and a distance in equation (i) and (ii) respectively, k nearest neighbor (K-NN) search finds the (k) closest points in x to a query point or set of points y .

Given a number of columns of x to be less than 15 (for simplicity sake) the equidistance is calculated and the label is predicted as shown in equation (i). The clustering diagram below further explains the classification model and label prediction. However, if the number of x is more than 15, the Exhaustive Searcher model is employed, this model considers the either the hamming distance, angles, correlation, spearman, jaccard, seclidean, mehalanobis or custom distance function for classification.

Figure 1: main page of the system

v. *Output form design*

The output result is the resultant effect of the implemented image processing toolbox and recognition techniques. This results starts with the dataset of the suspected identities, then the image processing results like the histogram equalization, filtration, feature extraction and recognition result will all be presented as the output result.

Figure 2: dataset for suspected identities

Figure 3: query image

Figure 4: histogram equalization

Figure 5: Program flow chart/ algorithm

Figure 4.10: proposed dataflow diagram of the system

3. System design platform

The design was implemented on MATLAB. This is a powerful language platform for technical computing, machine learning, and computer vision. It offers a user-friendly environment that combines computation, visualization, and programming, allowing users to express problems and solutions using familiar mathematical notation. MATLAB enables various functionalities such as matrix manipulations, plotting of functions and data, algorithm implementation, user interface creation, and interfacing with other programming languages like C, C++, Java, FORTRAN, and Python.

When applying MATLAB in image processing techniques, it represents an intensity image as a single matrix. Each element of the matrix corresponds to a pixel in the image, and the values in the intensity matrix represent different intensities or gray levels. An intensity of 0 represents black, while an intensity of 1 represents the full intensity or the white part of the image. This matrix representation allows for efficient manipulation and analysis of image data using MATLAB's extensive range of tools and functions.

4. Conclusion

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This work introduces a new approach to enhance digital forensic investigations by utilizing artificial intelligence, specifically machine learning, to improve face recognition systems. The K-NN (K-nearest neighbors) classifier is employed to train and classify features extracted from both query and class images using the Euclidean model. The algorithm generates a class of K nearest neighbor variables, which are labeled as the recognition result. The study suggests that further improvements can be achieved by utilizing neural networks instead of support vector machines, especially considering the limited number of images used in the dataset for training. Additionally, future work can focus on enhancing the recognition process's speed. The research demonstrates a recognition result of above 92% when tested with various images, showcasing the effectiveness of the approach.

By acknowledging the significance of intelligence and perceptions in this battle, Nigeria can pave the way towards achieving victory in the ongoing insurgency and setting a new paradigm for modern conflict resolution.

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